

EU-China joint action
to increase the development
and adoption of IPM tools

Consortium partners

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www.adopt-ipm.eu

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The background of the page is a vibrant green field of crops, likely corn, under bright sunlight. A large, semi-transparent, light-colored letter 'A' is overlaid on the left side of the image, extending from the top to the bottom. The text is positioned to the right of this 'A' shape.

ADOPT-IPM aims at the development, optimisation and implementation of Integrated Pest Management (IPM) tools and packages, and ultimately at the reduction of the dependency of farmers on conventional chemical pesticides in China, the EU Member States, and associated countries.

Funded by
the European Union

The project

While the use of chemical pesticides has largely contributed to boost the agricultural production for many years, their widespread use has negative impacts on the environment, human health, and non-target organisms. To address this critical issue, **environmentally-sound and sustainable pest management methods** need to be further developed and adopted by end users. Their adoption by farmers via IPM has been promoted by the EU since 2009, as well as by China's Ministry of Agriculture (MOA). Nevertheless, the adoption of IPM tools by farmers is slowed down by several major barriers.

Objectives and scope

In this context, the **ADOPT-IPM project seeks to**

Promote a global transition to sustainable agricultural systems, aiming at the development, optimisation and implementation of IPM tools and package, subsequently leading to a reduction in chemical pesticide use.

Simultaneously deliver the optimisation of existing IPM tools and the development of new ones.

Promote a rapid adoption by end users through the co-design of IPM packages with industrial partners, optimised for efficacy, profitability, and environmental sustainability, and through demonstration trials to end users.

ADOPT-IPM will focus on IPM against major arthropod pests, weeds and diseases in four key crops in the European Union and in China: **wheat, maize, tomato,** and **leafy vegetables.**

Activities

Since December 2022, **ADOPT-IPM works to:**

Optimise existing IPM tools and practices for major agricultural pests, diseases and weeds, and evaluate them against end users' expectations, to overcome the limits which currently prevent their widespread use

Develop new IPM tools considering farmers' and agricultural businesses' priorities, consumers' preferences and legislation-related issues.

Assess and demonstrate, through field trials, IPM tools and IPM packages under semi-field and commercial conditions, to accelerate the adoption of IPM packages at farm level in the EU and China.

Disseminate knowledge to key stakeholders, create a participatory framework that will ensure a continuous dialogue between researchers, extension specialists and end users, and support ADOPT-IPM SMEs within the exploitation and the regulatory process for IPM tools.

As global world trade has led to the globalisation of major pests on key crops for which environmentally-friendly pest management methods are yet limited and suboptimal, **the EU and China share similar objectives** to develop, optimise, and implement IPM tools against these key pests to reduce the use of chemical pesticides. The joint EU-China approach will allow a large-scale adoption of tailored IPM tools and packages, and enable agricultural products to be safer for domestic consumers, including products imported into the EU while ensuring profitable trade among countries.

